

Dyes derived from Phenanthraquinone.

Part VI.

Phenanthraquinone-phenyl azo-methines and Phenanthraphenazine-azo-dyes

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In continuation of the work of Watson and Dutta, (J. C. S., T. 1921, 119, 1211), Sircar and Dutta (J. C. S., T. 1922, 121, 1944), Sircar and Sircar (J. C. S., T. 1923, 123, 1559), Sircar and Roy (J. C. S., T. 1924, 125, 543), and Sircar and Dutt (J. I. C. S., 1924, 1, 201) the present investigation was undertaken with the object of making further attempts to prepare dyes from phenanthraquinone and its substituted derivatives.

Watson and Dutta (*loc. cit.*) prepared aminophenanthraphenazines in the hope that such compounds would be quinonoid in all possible tautomeric forms, would have long chains of conjugate linkings in their molecules, and would therefore be deep coloured dyes. (*cf.* Watson, J. C. S., T. 1914, 105, 759). But they were found to be all yellow. From these observations and from the difference in the colours of the aminophenanthraphenazines from those of the corresponding azonium compounds (Dutta, J. C. S., T. 1922, 121, 1952), one is naturally inclined towards the view that the amino-azine derivatives do not exist as outlined by Watson and Dutta (*loc. cit.*) in quinonoid tautomeric forms.

It has been shown that in an azonium compound like safranine both the amino groups cannot be diazotised at

the sametime in solution of acids of moderate strengths (*cf.* Jaubert, Ber., 28, 518, 1584, etc.), and this difference in the property of the amino groups in safranine is brought forward as an argument in favour of the view that in such a compound one of the amino groups only exists as such,—the other taking part in the formation of quinonoid structure. It was therefore thought that if 2:7-diaminophenanthra-phenazine was actually a tautomeric compound, as expected by Watson and Dutta, then both the amino groups, contained in it, would not be equally easily diazotisable. With the object of testing this, attempt was made to diazotise only one amino group of 2:7-diaminophenanthraphenazine. It was further thought that if mono-azo derivatives could be prepared from 2:7-diaminophenanthraphenazine, such bodies would possess well-developed and interesting tinctorial properties like those of the mono-azo compounds obtained from safranine (*e.g.*, diazine green, diazine blue and diazine black. Ger. Pat., 95, 668, etc.).

It has now been found that, contrary to expectation, both the amino groups in 2:7-diaminophenanthraphenazine are equally easily diazotisable. On taking only half the calculated quantity of sodium nitrite, half the molecules of the 2:7-diamino-azine taken were completely diazotised, the other half remaining unchanged. Evidently, in a compound like 2:7-diaminophenanthraphenazine, no distinction can be made between the two amino groups, and this goes to prove that the molecules of the amino-azines are not in quinonoid tautomeric state like the molecules of the corresponding azonium compounds.

The bis-azo derivatives obtained from 2:7-diaminophenanthraphenazine do not exhibit the same depth of colour as the mono-azo derivatives from safranine do.

The group —N=CH— when joined to the aromatic nuclei behaves as a chromophore like the—N=N—

(*i.e.*, azo) linking, and a number of azo-methine dyes possessing fairly developed tinctorial properties are known (*cf.* Green and Sen, J. C. S., T. 1910, 97, 2242; Morgan and Reeves, J. C. S., T. 1922, 121, 1). It was therefore thought that if azo-methine derivatives could be prepared from the aminophenanthraquinones by condensing them with various aldehydes, such bodies might also possess interesting tinctorial properties. With that object in view 2-amino-, 4-amino-, 2:7-diamino-, and 4:5-diamino-phenanthraquinones have been condensed with one or more of the following:—benzaldehyde, *p*-tolyl-aldehyde, cinnamic aldehyde, anisic aldehyde, salicylic aldehyde, resorcylic aldehyde, dimethyl-*para*-amino-benzaldehyde, *m*-nitro-benzaldehyde, bromo-salicylic aldehyde, *para*-chlorobenzaldehyde and vanillin.

The phenanthraquinone-phenyl-azo-methines are easily obtained in well-defined crystalline forms and most of them are fairly deep coloured, but they are not satisfactory so far as their dyeing properties are concerned. They possess no affinity for cotton and are decomposed into the original amino-quinone and the aldehyde when boiled for some time with water in presence of an acid. In attempting to dye wool with these bodies from a bath containing one per cent. sulphuric acid (calculated on the weight of the wool), it was found that in every case they decomposed at the temperature of boiling water, and the colours of the dyeings obtained were invariably those of the aminophenanthraquinones. Wool can, however, be dyed with them from an one per cent. acetic acid bath between 70° to 80°C, but the absorption of the dye is very slow and the dye-bath is never exhausted. Consequently full shades are not obtained on wool even by this method.

It has been noticed, in the course of this investigation, that both the amino groups in 2:7-diaminophenanthraquinone reacts with aldehydes only when they are heated

together alone (*i.e.*, in the absence of any solvent). On the other hand in the presence of a solvent only one of the amino group reacts with aldehyde, even when there is an excess of the latter.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phenanthraphenazine-2 : 7-bis-(1'-azo-2'-naphthol)—62 Grams of 2 : 7-diaminophenanthraphenazine, dissolved in 10 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid (sp. gr. 1.15) and cooled to 0°C, was diazotised in the usual way, and the diazo solution added to an ice-cold solution of 0.6 grams of β -naphthol with 5 grams of caustic soda. The solution, which at once became violet, was stirred for one hour and left over-night. Next day the dye-stuff was precipitated by the addition of dilute hydrochloric acid. It was then filtered, washed and boiled under reflux to remove excess of β -naphthol. All attempts to crystallise it from various solvents were unsuccessful.

It does not melt up to 300°C; is slightly soluble in ether or alcohol, more soluble in acetic acid, acetone, pyridine or nitrobenzene. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a reddish-violet colour, and dyes wool in reddish-violet shades from an acid-bath and cotton in pinkish shades from a neutral bath. (Found: N=13.52. $C_{40}H_{24}O_2N_6$ requires N=13.51 per cent.).

Phenanthraphenazine-2 : 7-bis-(1'-azo-2'-hydroxy-3'-naphthoic acid) was prepared from 2 : 7-diaminophenanthraphenazine (1 mol.) and 2'-hydroxy-3'-naphthoic acid (2 mols.) in the same way as the preceding compound.

It dyes wool in violet shades from an acid bath and cotton in light violet shades from a neutral bath. In its other properties it resembles the preceding compound (Found: N=12.26. $C_{48}H_{24}O_6N_7$ requires N=11.6 per cent.).

2-Amino-phenanthraquinone-7-(1'-azomethine-4'-dimethylamino-benzene) $(2)\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{N}(7) : \text{CH}(1') \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{N}(\text{Me})_2(4')$.—Separate solutions of 4 grams of 2:7-diaminophenanthraquinone and 3 grams of dimethyl-*para*-amino-benzal-dehyde in moderately strong hydrochloric acid, were mixed together and well-shaken, when the hydrochloride separated as a reddish precipitate. This was filtered, washed with water, then suspended in water and the free base liberated by the addition of ammonia. This separated from hot pyridine, on the addition of hot water, as shining, blue-black long needles, not melting below 300°C.

It is insoluble in ether or alcohol, and soluble in acetone, nitrobenzene or pyridine. It gives a yellowish-brown colour with concentrated sulphuric acid and dyes wool in bottle-green shades from acetic acid bath. (Found: $\text{N} = 11.66$. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires $\text{N} = 11.38$ per cent.).

2-Amino-phenanthraquinone-7-(1'-azo-methine-3': 4'-dihydroxy-benzene) was obtained as black needles from 2:7-diamino-phenanthraquinone (1 mol.) and resorcylic aldehyde (1 mol.) in the same way as, and possesses similar properties to, the preceding compound. (Found: $\text{N} = 8.07$. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires $\text{N} = 7.82$ per cent.).

The following five phenyl-azo-methines were prepared, in the same way, by heating the amino-quinone with excess of the aldehyde for half-an-hour under reflux. The crystals, coming out on cooling, were further purified by first washing with ether and then boiling with alcohol for some time. They form most beautiful and shining crystals, and possess similar properties. They are insoluble in ether or alcohol, but soluble in acetone, nitrobenzene or pyridine. They dissolve in strong sulphuric acid with a brown colour and dye wool in reddish-violet shades from acetic acid bath. They do not melt below 300°C.

Phenanthraquinon-2 : 7-bis-(1'-azo-methine-benzene), $C_{14}H_8O_2(N=CH-C_6H_5)_2$ —was obtained, as shining violet prisms, from 2 : 7-diaminophenanthraquinone (.4 grams) and benzaldehyde (10 c. c.). (Found: $N=7.26$. $C_{22}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires $N=6.76$ per cent.).

Phenanthraquinone-2 : 7-bis-(1'-azo-methine-4'-methylbenzene), prepared from 2 : 7-diaminophenanthraquinone and *p*-tolyl-aldehyde, separated as brilliant needle-shaped crystals of coppery lustre. (Found: $N=6.75$. $C_{30}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires $N=6.33$ per cent.).

Phenanthraquinone-2 : 7-bis-(azo-cinnamylidinemethine), obtained from 2 : 7-diaminophenanthraquinone and cinnamic aldehyde, crystallised in shining violet needles. (Found: $N=5.71$. $C_{22}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires $N=6.008$ per cent.).

Phenanthraquinone-2 : 7-bis-(1'-azo-methine-4'-methoxybenzene), prepared from the 2 : 7-diaminoquinone and anisic aldehyde, was obtained as shining reddish violet prisms. (Found: $N=6.00$. $C_{30}H_{22}O_4N_2$ requires $N=5.90$ per cent.).

Phenanthraquinone-2 : 7-bis-(1'-azo-methine-2'-hydroxybenzene), was obtained, as brilliant, needle-shaped, shining scarlet crystals, by the condensation of the 2 : 7-diaminoquinone (.4 grams) with salicylic aldehyde (10 c. c.). (Found: $N=6.14$. $C_{28}H_{18}O_4N_2$ requires $N=6.27$ per cent.).

2-Acetyl aminophenanthraquinone-7-(1'-azo-methine-2'-hydroxybenzene).—The pinkish-white precipitate produced on adding 2 c. c. of salicylic aldehyde to a solution of .4 grams of 2 : 7-diaminophenanthraquinone in 20 c. c. of glacial acetic acid changed, on heating for a few minutes under reflux, to beautiful violet prismatic needle-shaped crystals. These were filtered, washed first with water and finally with ether. From a study of its properties it appears that the amino group in 2 position has been acetylated during the reaction.

It does not melt below 300°C. It is insoluble in ether, alcohol or acetone and soluble in pyridine. It is very sparingly soluble in cold concentrated hydrochloric acid, but moderately soluble in the boiling acid to a red solution which on dilution turns yellow, without any reprecipitation of the original substance. It is slightly soluble in caustic soda solution in the cold, but more soluble on warming. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a blood-red colouration and dyes wool in violet shades from acetic acid bath. (Found: N=6.95. $C_{22}H_{14}O_4N_2$ requires N=7.29 per cent.).

2-Amino-phenanthraquinone-7-(1'-azo-methine-2'-hydroxy-benzene), separated as reddish-violet needles on allowing to stand for 24 hours a solution of .4 gram of 2:7-diamino-phenanthraquinone and 2 c.c. of salicylic aldehyde in 25 c.c. of absolute alcohol, and was further purified first by washing with ether and then by boiling for sometime with alcohol under reflux. It was found to contain a molecule of alcohol associated with it. It resembles the preceding compound in its properties (Found: N=7.26. $C_{21}H_{14}O_5N_2 \cdot C_2H_5OH$ requires N=7.21 per cent.).

Phenanthraquinone-4-(1-azo-methine-3'-nitro-benzene), was obtained from 4-aminophenanthraquinone (.4 grams) and *meta*-nitrobenzaldehyde (.3 grams) by boiling in glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.) for half-an-hour. The precipitate crystallised from pyridine in orange-red minute needles, not melting below 300°C. It dyes wool in chocolate shades from acetic acid bath. (Found: N=8.18. $C_{21}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires N=7.86 per cent.).

The following compounds were prepared in a similar way, and resemble the preceding compound in properties.

Phenanthraquinone-2-(1'-azo-methine-3'-nitro-benzene) was obtained as brownish-black crystals from 2-amino-phenanthraquinone and *meta*-nitrobenzaldehyde (Found: N=8.68. $C_{21}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires N=7.86 per cent.).

4-Amino-phenanthraquinone-5-(1'-azo-methine-3'-nitro-benzene), prepared from 4 : 5-diaminophenanthra-quinone (.4 grams) and *meta*-nitrobenzaldehyde (.6 grams), could not be obtained crystalline. It was purified from nitrobenzene and obtained as an amorphous violet powder, not melting below 300°C. (Found : N=11.58. $C_{21}H_{13}O_4N_3$ requires N=11.32 per cent.).

2-Amino-phenanthraquinone-7-(1'-azo-methine-3'-nitro-benzene), prepared from 2 : 7-diaminophenanthraquinone (.4 grams) and *meta*-nitrobenzaldehyde (.6 grams), crystallised out of nitrobenzene in violet needles. (Found : N=11.84. $C_{21}H_{13}O_4N_3$ requires N=11.32 per cent.).

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